

**THE ROLE OF IT TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING
ENGLISH TO TEENAGERS**

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Abstract:

This article describes the methods of effective teaching of English among teenagers with technology and modern educational technologies.

Key words: language, independent language learning, English, technology, interest, project, activity, interesting programs and applications

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Today, the main attention is focused on the student and his personality and his effective education. Therefore, several modern technologies have been created for young people. The use of these technologies is very convenient and modern for young people. The main purpose of teaching foreign languages is to develop students' communicative culture and teach them to master a foreign language using easy and modern methods. In recent years, the number of people who need to learn English is increasing. Therefore, the number of modern technological methods is also sufficient.

Discussion and results

English can be learned easily and quickly in various ways. Including, during the lesson with the teacher, that is, practical learning. One of the main tasks of the teacher is to activate the student's knowledge in the process of teaching foreign languages. Adolescents have a great desire to learn a language. Therefore, if the teacher works in cooperation with the students by involving them in the lesson with the help of various modern methods, the level of learning and interest of the students will increase. In addition, in foreign language classes it will be appropriate to use computer training programs. Because today the possibilities of using internet resources are very large. The global internet makes it possible to get any information necessary for a student, that is, students can find information about the English language through any site or in newspapers and magazines. they can learn the language through information. Therefore, the Internet is one of the necessary resources for learning English. For example, using the Internet, there are various didactic problems can be discussed. In addition, there are several methods, especially for teenage students. Nowadays, several programs have been created for learning English, for example, Lingualeo, Duolingo, Polyglot, Memrise, BBC Learning English, Easy ten, WORDS, Learn ENGLISH grammar, Rosetta Stone, Voxy, Rememba, English Grammar in Use, 15,000 Useful Phrases, Word Book, Puzzle English.

1.Lingualeo. This app offers a popular service with a variety of exercises. These exercises help to expand vocabulary as well as develop reading, writing

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and listening skills. The exercises are based on gamification and stimulate interest in English. always urges to strive.

2. Duolingo. This application teaches English in the form of a game by spending a few minutes a day. You start with simple verbs and phrases, and slowly the exercises are based on grammar.

3. Polyglot. This application belongs to Dmitry Petrov, the author of the course of the same name, a well-known polyglot. According to him, the program allows you to master the English language at a basic level in 16 lessons. By spending at least 15 minutes a day, you can learn the rules of grammar. you will learn to remember the necessary words and communicate freely, and most importantly, you will learn to make phrases.

4. Memrise. This app is another game-like program that turns English into a fun activity and makes memorizing new words easier. The curator of the Memrise adventure world invites you to travel through a world full of mysteries. During this journey, you will be given mysterious tasks. and the world of enemies awaits you, along the way you will be helped by wonderful assistants.

5. BBC Learning English. This program is the official application of BBC 'C. It collects materials from radio and television programs of various broadcasting corporations to learn English. In addition to audio content, you can learn grammar, make phrases and learn words. There are a variety of exercises to master.

6. Easy ten. With the help of this program, you will memorize 10 new words by performing the given lexical exercise every day. App does not require a lot of time; it is enough to spend 20 minutes a day. The program contains more than 20 thousand words, and there are also special exercises that help improve pronunciation. You can also categorize new words into thematic lists and track your progress for extra motivation.

7. Words. It's not by chance that this app fell into the best category of "Education" in the AppStore. The database of the program contains more than 8,000 words and it can be used offline. The main advantage of the application is that it adapts to the user's level, identifies words that caused difficulty before, and then in the exercises, those words are given until you remember them.

8. Learn ENGLISH Grammar. This application is very useful for teenage learners. It is an application offered by the British Consulate to improve English. It is aimed at learning grammar and helps you to reach any level.

9. Rosetta Stone This app mainly focuses on memorizing new words. The application is provided for free, but there are also paid materials.

10. Voxy. what makes this app different from other apps is that it adapts to your needs and preferences in real time. Do you want to prepare for TOEFL? This application is very important because through this application you will not only prepare but also improve your pronunciation

11. Rememba. A convenient program specially created for memorizing new words

12. English Grammar in Use. An application aimed at developing grammar from Cambridge University Press.

13. 15 000 Useful Phrases. a program designed to learn words and phrases used in everyday communication.

14. WordBook The dictionary works in offline mode

15. Puzzle ENGLISH. Videos and audios for learning English.

Each of the mentioned programs are very convenient and modern programs. Through this, teenage learners can learn English independently. Therefore, the

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global Internet plays an important role. Above the indicated modern technological methods and programs make it possible to learn the language in depth.

Conclusions and Suggestions. Today, 1.5 billion people around the world speak English. Most of them are young people, i.e. learners. English differs from other languages in its pronunciation and grammar. The number of people who have studied and are studying is also large because modern dog technologies have a great role.

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